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ON A PROBLEM OF STATISTICAL MODELING OF A HYDRODYNAMIC SYSTEM WITH DISTRIBUTED PARAMETERS

(in relation to mineral deposits)

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Abstract The article considers the applied problem of software management for analyzing the state of the system. The state of the system (pressure field) is described by an elliptic partial differential equation. An estimate of the solutions of the boundary value problem in a limited range of parameter changes is obtained. The results can be used in the development and operation of oil and gas fields

Keywords: Differential equation, elliptic type, boundary conditions, Laplace operator, states of the system, displacement estimation, rules of “wandering through the sphere”, Markov chain, permissible sphere, fundamental solution, uniform distribution, unit sphere.

During the operation of oil and gas fields, as well as in the processes of underground leaching in mining fields, the productive reservoir and the wells located in it can be represented as a single hydrodynamic system with distributed parameters (parameters change in space and time), and the state of the system itself is described by partial differential equations. Thus, the formation and the well are like a hydrodynamic control system with distributed parameters [1,2]

When determining the modes of operation of the system, it is necessary to solve applied problems of software management, i.e. determining the state of the system in space and time. The state of the system (pressure field) is described by an elliptic partial differential equation

$$L(A) = - \sum_{i,j=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (K_{i,j}(x) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x_j}) = 0, x \in D. \quad (1)$$

Here D - limited area n - of dimensional space R_1^n , the infinitely smooth boundary of which consists of an outer contour Γ_0 and internal contours $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \dots, \Gamma_n$ - well contours (in the case of a flat formation $n = 2$). Coefficients $K(x) = kb / \mu = const$ - the complex of filtration parameters (k - the permeability coefficient of the productive reservoir, b - reservoir capacity, μ - the viscosity coefficient of the liquid).

The pressure on the outer contour of the area is set as

$$u(x) = u_0(x), \quad x \in \Gamma_0, \quad (2)$$

on the contour of wells

$$\oint_{\Gamma_i} \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} ds = q_i, \quad i = \overline{1, n}, \quad (3)$$

где q_i - well flow rates.

Equation (1) was solved under various boundary conditions by statistical tests using the “grid walk” rule [3,6,7].

In this paper, we propose the application of a well-known statistical test method - “wandering through spheres” [4,5].

To solve the boundary value problem (1) – (3), we introduce a new function

$$p = \frac{kb}{\mu} u(x), \quad p = p(x),$$

then equation (1) has the form:

$$\Delta p = 0, \quad (4)$$

where Δ is the Laplace operator.

We introduce a number of designations and definitions. Let

$$\bar{D} = \sum_{i=1}^m \{x : |x - w_i| < r_i\} \quad (5)$$

- a single-connected area limited to only one Γ , here w_i and r_i accordingly, the center and radius of the contour Γ_i ;

$$\Omega = \{w_i\} \quad i = \overline{1, n},$$

$$V_R(x) = \{x' : |x - x'| < R\}, \quad (6)$$

$$w_R = \{x' : |x - x'| = R\}.$$

Let's define the number $\delta(D)$, which characterizes the measure of well density as follows:

$$\delta(D) = \min \left\{ \min_{i \neq j} |w_i - w_j|, \min_i \rho(w_i, \Gamma) \right\}, \quad (7)$$

$\rho(w_i, \Gamma)$ - distance between sets w_i и Γ

Definition. The sphere $w_R(x)$ centered at a point $x \in \overline{D}$ it is called an acceptable sphere, if $w_R(x) \in \overline{D}$ and there is inequality

$$\rho(w_R(x), \Omega) > \frac{\delta(D)}{16n}.$$

Statement 1. For any $x \in \overline{D}$ there is a valid scope

$w_R(x)$, moreover, the radius of this sphere satisfies the inequality

$$R > \min \{d(x), \delta(\overline{D})/8\}. \quad (8)$$

Proof. Let $d(x) > \delta(D)/4$. Let's define the set

$$A_s(x) = V_{R_s}(x) \setminus V_{R_{s-1}}(x),$$

where

$$R_s = \frac{d(x)}{2} + s \frac{d(x)}{2 * 2n}, \quad s = \overline{1, 2n+1}$$

It is known that A_s the sets do not intersect in pairs and their number is equal

$2n+1$. Plenty $\Omega = \{w_i\} \quad i = \overline{1, n}$, has n elements, therefore, there is such a thing S_0 , as in the sets A_{S_0} и A_{S_0+1} there are no elements from Ω . If we define

$$R = \frac{d(x)}{2} + s_0 \frac{d(x)}{4n},$$

that's for R the inequality is fulfilled (8) and the sphere $w_R(x)$ is acceptable.

When $d(x) < \delta(D)/4$, then assuming $R = d(x)$ we get the required radius of the sphere. Statement 1 has been proven.

In the future, we will count everywhere, what

$$\frac{\delta(D)}{16} \gg \max_{i=1,n} R_i,$$

Let $x_0 \in D$, и $w_{R_0}(x_0)$ - acceptable scope. Using the fundamental solution of the Laplace operator, it is easy to get an idea

$$p(x_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi R_0} \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} p(x) ds_x + \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_r(x_0, w_i) \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{R_0}{|x-x_0|} \frac{\partial p(x)}{\partial n} ds_x + \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_{R_0}(x_0, w_i) \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} \frac{p(x) \cos \psi_{x_0, x}^{(i)}}{2\pi |x-x_0|} ds_x \quad (9)$$

where $\psi_{x_0, x}^{(i)}$ - the angle between the normal to the contour Γ_i and vectors $x-x_0$

$$\chi(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, \text{если } |x-y| < 1 \\ 0, \text{если } |x-y| \geq 1 \end{cases}.$$

Let u_i - the average value of the function $u(x)$ in the inner contour Γ_i , т.е.

$$p_i = \frac{1}{2\pi r_i} \oint_{w_{r_0}(x)} p(x) ds_x. \quad (10)$$

Thus, from (10) we get:

$$\oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} \frac{\cos \psi_{x_0, x}^{(i)}}{2\pi |x-x_0|} ds_x = 0, (x \in D),$$

and from (9) we get:

$$p(x_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi R_0} \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} p(x) ds(x) + \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_{R_0}(x_0, \omega_i) \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \frac{R_0}{|\omega_i - x_0|} + \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_{R_0}(x_1, w_i) \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \frac{|w_i - x|}{|x - x_0|} \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} ds_x + \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_{R_0}(x, \omega_i) \oint_{\Gamma_i} \frac{p(x) \cos \psi_{x_0, x}^{(i)}}{2\pi |x-x_0|} \cos \psi_{x_0, x_1}^{(i)} ds_x. \quad (11)$$

Since

$$\frac{d_0}{d_0 + r_i} < \frac{|\omega_i - x_0|}{|x - x_0|} < \frac{d_0}{d_0 - r_i},$$

by $d_0 \gg \max r_i$
 $i = \overline{1, n}$

we will get $\left| \ln \frac{|\omega_i - x_0|}{|x - x_0|} \right| < \frac{r_i}{d_0}$.

From (10) and (11) we get:

$$u(x_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi R_0} \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} u(x) ds_x + \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_R(x_0, \omega_i) \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \frac{R_0}{|\omega_i - x_0|} + \alpha(x_0), \quad (12)$$

where $|\alpha(x_0)| < \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{r_i^2}{d_0} \max \left| \frac{du}{dn} \right| + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{r_i}{d_0} \max_{\Gamma_i} |u - u_i|$.

If $x_0 = \omega_i$, then in a similar way we have:

$$u_i = \frac{1}{2\pi R_0} \oint_{w_{R_0}(x)} u(x) ds_x + \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{R_0}{r_i} \right) + \sum_{i \neq j} \chi_{R_0}(x_0, \omega_j) \frac{q_j}{2\pi} \ln \frac{R_0}{|\omega_j - x_0|} + \beta(x), \quad (13)$$

where to $\beta(x)$ There is also inequality (8). But instead of d_0 It is necessary to substitute $\delta(D)$, t.e.

$$|\beta(x_0)| < \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{r_i^2}{\delta(D)} \max_{\Gamma_i} \left| \frac{du}{dn} \right| + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{r_i}{\delta(D)} \max_{\Gamma_i} |u - u_i|$$

Let $\delta_0 = \frac{\delta(D)}{16n}, \delta_1 = \frac{\delta(D)}{8}$.

Let's build a Markov chain starting from the point x_0 , according to the recurrent formula $x_n = x_{n-1} + \bar{\omega}_n R_{n-1}$,

where is the sequence ω_n - isotropic independent vectors uniformly distributed on a unit sphere.

Regarding the Markov chain, we will make two assumptions:

- a) $R_n > \min \{d(x_n), \delta\}$;
- b) $\rho(w_{R_n}(x_m), \Omega) > \delta_0, m = 1, 2, \dots$.

It follows from statement 1 that for any point $x \in \bar{D}$ You can build a chain $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ according to rule (13), for which condition a) and b) are fulfilled.

In the future, we will assume that the chain satisfies the conditions a) and b).

$$\text{Let } \varepsilon > 0 \text{ и } \Gamma_\varepsilon = \{x \in D : \rho(x, \Gamma) < \varepsilon\},$$

where ε - the vicinity of the border. Let's introduce the moment when the particles stop

$$N_\varepsilon = \min\{n : x_0 \in \Gamma_\varepsilon\}$$

for the Markov chain $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$.

Let's build the following estimate

$$\xi_\varepsilon(x_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{N_\varepsilon-1} f(x_n) + \varphi(\bar{x}_\varepsilon), \quad (14)$$

where x_ε - the nearest point from the outer boundary Γ к X_{N_ε} ,

$$f(x_0) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_{R_0, \omega_i} \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \frac{R_0}{|x - \omega_i|}, \text{если } x_0 \in D, \\ \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{R_0}{r_{i_0}} \right) + \sum_{i \neq j} \chi_{R_0}(x_0, \omega_i) \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \frac{R}{|x_0 - \omega_i|}, \text{если } x_0 = \omega_{i_0} \end{array} \right\}, \quad (15)$$

$$f(x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \chi_{R_n}(x_n, \omega_i) \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \frac{R_n}{|x_n - \omega_i|}, n = 1, 2, \dots, \quad (16)$$

It is not difficult to make sure that when the condition is met,
 Statement 2.

Statement 2. For the moment of stopping N_ε evaluation is in progress

$$MN_\varepsilon < C |\ln \varepsilon|,$$

where is the constant C it depends only on the properties of the border Γ .

It is noticeable that the function $f(x)$ in the definition, the estimate (14) is limited from above by the number

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{d}{\delta_0} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{q_i}{2\pi} \ln \left(\frac{d}{r_i} \right) \geq f(x_n), \quad (17)$$

where α - the diameter of the area D , and also as in [5] the following statements can be proved.

Statement 3. Variance of the estimate ξ_ε uniformly bounded.

Lemma. Let $x_0 \in D$ and $\min_{i=1, n} \rho(x_0, \Gamma_i) = d_0$, then for the offset

$$|p(x_0) - M_{\xi_\varepsilon}(x_0)|$$

evaluations (14), inequality is fair:

$$\begin{aligned} |p(x_0) - M_{\xi_\varepsilon}(x_0)| < \sup |p(x) + \psi(\bar{x})| + e \left| \ln \varepsilon \right| \left(\frac{1}{d_0} + \frac{1}{\delta_0} \right) \sum_{i=1}^n r_i^2 \max_{\Gamma_i} \left| \frac{dp}{dn} \right| + \\ + r_i \max_{\Gamma_i} |u - u_i| \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Proof. ..If $x_0 = \omega_i$, then an evaluation is also performed

$$|p_i - \xi_\varepsilon(\omega_i)| < \sup_{x \in \Gamma_\varepsilon} |u(x) - \psi(\bar{x})| + \frac{C |\ln \varepsilon|}{\delta_0} \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i^2 \max_i \left| \frac{dp}{dn} \right| + r_i \max_i |p - p_i|), \quad (19)$$

where $\bar{x} \in \Gamma$ the nearest point $\kappa x \in \Gamma_\varepsilon$ and the constant C it depends only on the border Γ .

Proof of inequality (18) it flows easily from (12), (13) and (15),(16).

The obtained estimation of solutions of the partial differential equation (1) in a limited range of parameter changes with boundary conditions (2), (3) They can be used in solving applied problems of analyzing the states of systems with distributed parameters that occur during the development and operation of oil and gas fields, as well as in hydrodynamic processes of underground leaching.

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